

Future visions of a sister city with nature

Game materials

Role cards	DIN A5
Welcome poster	DIN A2
Vision	DIN A5
Postcard	DIN A5
Harvesting Poster	DIN A1

Role card

You are an **OAK**.

In the northern hemisphere, you are one of the most important deciduous trees. Your branches form a spreading crown and your bark is thick and cracked. You especially like mineral-rich and fresh soils where your deep roots can spread widely. You are relatively undemanding and can survive drought as well as waterlogging, but you need a lot of sun and warmth. What you cannot handle are nutrient deficiencies, polluted and over-acidified soils.

In spring your leaves sprout and your flowers open, and then in autumn your fruits, the acorns, ripen. These are an important food source for many animals in winter, like birds or rodents. In addition, you and your deadwood are an indispensable habitat for countless species of other animals. Thanks to you, mankind has also survived difficult times by using your acorns to make flour or coffee substitutes. But you also have enemies like the caterpillars from the oak processionary moth, that want to eat your crown completely bare. Due to climate change, these animals are multiplying.

Role card

You are the **RIVER** _____.

From a small spring you become a very large river with the help of many mountain streams. To have enough space to develop dynamically you prefer to be completely unchanged. You are an indispensable habitat for many beings. Therefore, it is also very important that there are no obstacles such as gates or dams in your way. Pollution and trash harm you and the beings that live in and around you.

You swing yourself through the landscape, with a wide cross profile. Your many backwaters and side channels, sandbanks, and islands foster habitat diversity. Silver willows, alders, ash trees, and black poplars grow on your lightly shaded banks. Floodplains in your immediate neighborhood protect land dwellers from flooding by storing water.

Role card

You are an **EARTH BUMBLEBEE.**

After surviving the winter, you are now looking for food and a nesting place to establish your own state. You feel at home almost everywhere, you like to be in open landscapes or in sparse forests. For your nesting place you look for an underground cave, such as an abandoned mouse nest. You are also not very selective in your choice of food, you can get pollen and nectar from many different plants. That is why you are one of the most important pollinator insects.

The workers, drones, and young queens hatch in your nest now. At the end of the summer you will die together with your state.

Cuckoos are not among your friends, they lay their eggs in your nests and try to displace you. But your biggest enemy is industrial agriculture, insecticides and monocultures which cause you trouble. That is why you are always happy about a garden that blooms all year long and where you can find piles of stones and deadwood to nest in.

Role card

You are a **HUMAN BEING.**

Since you are very adaptable, you can be found almost everywhere in the world whereby most of you live in urban areas. Your abilities have helped you to make different ecosystems accessible for yourself. Besides food, community, closeness, and physical activity are especially important to you. You try to make yourself less dependent on natural conditions. Accordingly, you change your environment in such a way that your needs are satisfied. For that, you build roads and permanent dwellings for instance. Especially the small beings of your kind are dependent within your communities.

Through your consciousness you can perceive temporal and historical dimensions and reflect on yourself and your actions. However, in many cultures you lost your connection with nature, perceiving yourself as superior to animals for instance which strongly harms yourself and your environment. For example, you need many materials and resources for your projects. By this, you often intervene negatively in natural-driven cycles.

Role card

You are an **EARTHWORM**.

The vibrations of the raindrops lure you to the surface of the earth, where you are exposed to many dangers such as hungry blackbirds, shrews or UV light. That is why you prefer to stay underground, digging through the damp soil of meadows and gardens.

However, you avoid soils acidified by fertilizers. Your burrows serve as your living space. For you to be able to dig so diligently, temperatures should be between 10 and 20 degrees Celsius. If it is hotter or colder, you dig deep into the earth and go into a kind of summer or winter sleep.

You feed on leaves, dead plant debris and microorganisms, which you then excrete as nutrient-rich droppings. This excrement and your digging make you especially popular in human gardens. This is because you ensure that the soil is well aerated, nutrients reach the top and there is no waterlogging. Thus, plant roots and soil organisms can live well in the soil you loosen.

Role card

You are a **DOG**.

You are descended from the wolf, domesticated by mankind a long time ago. Today you are one of the most popular pets. Besides you, there are many different breeds around the world. You not only provide companionship, but also take on other tasks as guide dogs, herding dogs, search dogs, guard dogs, hunting dogs or drug-sniffing dogs.

As pack animal, you are very social and enjoy being in the company of people, preferably while moving. Another one of your favourite activities is eating. You can reproduce year-round and have your offspring in your belly for about nine to ten weeks, giving birth to up to 15 puppies, who cannot see or hear anything for the first few weeks.

Unfortunately, you often do not have that much self-determination over your life. Most decisions are made by people for you. Despite the many humans who love you, they can also be your undoing if they abandon you or treat you badly.

Visions of a sister city with nature

**Welcome to the first sister city with nature,
welcome to the future!**

How will urban life look and feel like in the future?

How will our relationship with nature change?

We aim to transform a city made for humans into a place in which all living beings are welcome. Therefore, we will work with the vision of a human-nature partnership as an alternative to dominance and hierarchy. Together we will try to create meaningful narratives and gain precious insights about urban human-nature relationships, enriched by perspectives of non-human beings.

Phases

Vision

Welcome to _____ in the future!

The river and its side streams make their way through the green city of _____. Human residents appreciate the diverse and vibrant urban nature that surrounds them in everyday life. The services but also the limits of the usability of urban ecosystems are acknowledged and form the foundation for political decisions and urban strategies.

Welcome to the regenerative city!

The use of natural resources, such as water or soil, is based on the reciprocal principle of giving and taking. This is visible in the many regional circular systems that ensure a resilient and regenerative city. The image of a good life is no longer linked to constantly expanding one's own material wealth. For example, companies support the sharing of resources and align their actions with the common good. The city is independent of fossil fuels and the new lifestyle is reflected in an improvement in the quality of life. Living in _____ is nice, it is quiet, the air is not polluted, and the available space is shared by all kinds of living beings. Interaction is characterized by respect and recognition of the limits of nature's availability. This can be seen, for example, in the rise of local food consumption and in resonant relations with the annual and regenerative seasons of the fields and plants. Human needs for regeneration and rest are equally respected and their importance is demonstrated by the numerous urban places of contemplation.

Welcome to the just healthy city!

City dwellers respect that the well-being of humans depends on the well-being of non-human nature. A new holistic understanding of health considers the interactions between mental and physical dimensions and its interconnectedness with the health of other living beings and whole ecosystems. Mutual care is based on a shared understanding of community and belonging between human and non-human beings. Both inside and outside the city, flora and fauna, water bodies and landscapes are recognized as legal persons, so that exploitative and destructive practices are punishable. In _____, specially trained representatives of non-human beings make their needs and spatial demands visible. They are involved in decision-making processes at various levels as mandate holders and ensure the general interest in the well-being of non-human nature as equal relationship partners.

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Role play by URBNANCE Team, <https://urbance.iner.info/>, Layout: Stefanie Klein

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